

Kinetic and thermodynamic investigations of adsorption of fluoride onto activated *Aloe vera* carbon

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Abstract : Batch sorption system using activated *Aloe vera* carbon as an adsorbent was investigated to remove fluoride ions from aqueous solutions. The system variables studied include initial concentration of the sorbate, agitation time, pH, co-ions and temperature. The experimental data fitted well to the Freundlich and Langmuir isotherms. Thermodynamic parameters such as ΔH° , ΔS° and ΔG° were calculated indicating that the adsorption was spontaneous and endothermic. A mechanism involving intra particle diffusion and surface adsorption has been proposed for the adsorption of F^- onto the adsorbent. XRD patterns of the adsorbent were recorded to get a better in sight into the mechanism of adsorption process.

Keywords : *Aloe vera* carbon, adsorption, fluoride ion.

Endemic skeletal fluorosis continues to be a public health problem in several parts of the world where drinking water contains naturally occurring soluble fluoride much above the permissible limit of 1.5 mg/L¹. Current methods used to remove fluoride from water can be divided into two categories : precipitation and adsorption. Precipitation of fluoride with calcium and aluminium salts has been used to remove fluoride from industrial wastewater. Typically, lime is used as a calcium source and the Ca^{II} ions released interact with fluoride and form CaF_2 precipitate. The aluminium salts interact with fluoride in water and form AlF_n^{3-n} and $Al(OH)_{3-m}F_m$ etc.². Adsorption is another technique, in which fluoride is adsorbed onto a membrane, or a fixed bed packed with resin or other mineral particles.

Many techniques have been reported, such as reverse osmosis, electro dialysis, Donnan dialysis, ion exchange, limestone reactor and activated alumina column³. The efficiency of this technique mainly depends on adsorbents. Recent attention of researchers has been devoted to the study of low cost and at the same time effective materials⁴. The objective of the present endeavor, therefore, is to study the adsorption behavior of fluoride onto activated *Aloe vera* carbon (AVC), an economically viable and easily available adsorbent. Further, *Aloe vera* skin is

a waste material from industries which manufacture naturopathy medicines and cosmetics.

Results and discussion

Sorbent characterization : The particle size of the adsorbent employed in the present study is 0.15 mm (100 mesh British standards). The zero point charge (pH_{ZPC}) of the adsorbent was found to be 6.7. The bulk density and moisture content of the carbon are 0.69 g/ml and 2.6%, respectively.

Effect of initial concentration : The results of equilibrium studies, the equilibrium concentration, C_{eq} (mg/L), quantity adsorbed, Q_{eq} (mg/g) and percentage of fluoride adsorbed, were collected in Table 1. The results revealed that, the amount adsorbed increases while the percentage removal decreases with the increase in initial concentration of fluoride ions. This indicates that there exists a reduction in immediate solute adsorption owing to the lack of available active sites on the adsorbent surface, compared with the relatively large number of active sites required for the high initial concentration of fluoride⁵. The percentage uptake is highly dependent on initial concentration of fluoride ions in the solution and it increase, at a fixed concentration of fluoride, with increase in temperature. This may be due to the fact that with increase in

Table 1. Equilibrium parameters for the adsorption of fluoride onto AVC

[F ⁻] ₀	C _{eq} (mg L ⁻¹)			Q _{eq} (mg g ⁻¹)			Fluoride removed (%)		
	30°	40°	50°	30°	40°	50°	30°	40°	50 °C
2	0.905	0.843	0.773	0.055	0.058	0.061	54.8	57.9	61.4
4	2.050	1.804	1.566	0.098	0.110	0.122	48.8	54.9	60.9
6	3.261	2.786	2.470	0.137	0.161	0.177	45.7	53.6	58.8
8	4.694	4.400	3.430	0.165	0.180	0.229	41.3	45.0	57.1
10	5.924	5.678	5.041	0.204	0.216	0.248	40.8	43.2	49.6

temperature the rate of adsorption may increase i.e. the adsorption process is endothermic in nature.

Adsorption isotherms : The adsorption isotherms generally used for the design of adsorption system. The Langmuir⁶ and Freundlich⁷ equations are commonly used for describing the adsorption isotherm. The linear equation of Langmuir and Freundlich are represented as follows eqs. (1) and (2), respectively.

$$C_{eq}/Q_{eq} = (C_{eq}/Q^0) + (1/Q^0b) \quad (1)$$

$$\log Q_{eq} = 1/n \log C_{eq} + \log K \quad (2)$$

where Q_{eq} and C_{eq} has the usual meanings and Q^0 (adsorption capacity) and b (energy of adsorption) are the Langmuir constants. K and n are the empirical constants of the Freundlich isotherm measuring the adsorption capacity and intensity of adsorption respectively.

The essential characteristics of the Langmuir equation can be described by a dimensionless equilibrium parameter, R_L , which is defined by Hall *et al.*⁸, as;

$$R_L = 1/(1 + bC_0) \quad (3)$$

where b is the Langmuir constant (L mg⁻¹) and C_0 is the initial fluoride ion concentration (mg L⁻¹). The value of R_L indicates the shape of the isotherms to be either unfavorable ($R_L > 1$), linear ($R_L = 1$), favorable ($0 < R_L < 1$) or irreversible ($R_L = 0$).

The Langmuir adsorption isotherms were studied at 30, 40 and 50 °C. The linear plots of C_{eq}/Q_{eq} versus C_{eq} at different temperatures indicate the applicability of the Langmuir adsorption isotherm. The value of isotherm constants and other statistical parameters were given in Table 2. The results indicate that the adsorption capacity increased with increasing temperature. The R_L values computed for the present system are provided in Table 3. The R_L values between 0 and 1 indicate favorable adsorption for all the initial concentrations and temperatures studied⁹.

The adsorption data have been fitted to the Freundlich isotherm. The linear plots of $\log Q_{eq}$ versus $\log C_{eq}$ at

Table 2. Langmuir and Freundlich isotherm constants

Isotherm	Statistical parameter/ constants	Temp. (°C)		
		30	40	50
Langmuir	r	0.979	0.978	0.939
	sd	1.24	1.26	1.33
	Q^0	0.389	0.382	0.563
Freundlich	b	0.171	0.225	0.173
	r	0.999	0.985	0.984
	sd	0.012	0.045	0.051
	K	0.059	0.070	0.081
	n	1.46	1.47	1.29

Table 3. Equilibrium parameter, R_L

Fluoride concentration (mg L ⁻¹)	Temp. (°C)		
	30	40	50
2	0.745	0.689	0.743
4	0.594	0.526	0.591
6	0.494	0.426	0.491
8	0.422	0.357	0.419
10	0.369	0.308	0.366

different temperatures indicate the applicability of Freundlich adsorption isotherm. The results (Table 2) indicates that the adsorption capacity (measured by K) of the adsorbent increases with increase in temperature. Further the value of intensity of adsorption (n) is greater than unity signifies that the forces within the surface layer are attractive¹⁰.

The Langmuir model deals with monolayer coverage and constant adsorption energy while Freundlich equation deals with physicochemical adsorption on heterogeneous surfaces¹¹. The applicability of both these isotherms to the activated carbon, in the present study, implies that both monolayer adsorption and heterogeneous surfaces conditions exist under the experimental conditions used. The adsorption properties of the adsorbent are thus likely to be complex, involve more than one mechanism¹².

Effect of pH : The effect of pH of medium on the

amount of fluoride ions adsorbed onto AVC was studied. The percent removal of fluoride at pH values 3, 5, 7, 9, 11 and 13 are 62.7, 61.3, 46.0, 43.8, 46.1 and 16.8% respectively. The results indicate that the adsorbent exhibits a commendable defluoridation capacity in acidic range of pH. This behavior can be explained on the basis of zero point charge ($\text{pH}_{\text{ZPC}} = 6.7$) of the adsorbent. At higher pH above this point, the OH^- ions compete effectively with fluoride ions causing a decrease in the amount of fluoride removed. At a lower pH below this zero point charge, the surface of the adsorbent gets positively charged, which enhances the adsorption of negatively charged fluoride ions through electrostatic force of attraction¹³⁻¹⁵.

Thermodynamic parameters : The standard free energy change, enthalpy and entropy changes along with equilibrium constants were computed as reported earlier⁵ and are given in Table 4. The endothermic nature of adsorption is indicated by a increase in K_o with rise in temperature. The results in Table 4 indicate that ΔG° values increase with increasing initial fluoride concentration. The ΔG° values are negative (at low fluoride concentration and high temperatures) which mean that the reaction is spontaneous, while the positive ΔG° values indicate non-spontaneous reactions. The values of enthalpy of a sorption process may be used to distinguish between chemical and physical sorption¹⁶. For chemical sorption, enthalpy values range from 83 to 830 kJ mol^{-1} , while for physical sorption they range from 8 to 25 kJ mol^{-1} . On the basis of the above distinction, fluoride ion sorption by AVC could be a physical process. Positive values of ΔH° suggest that the process is endothermic, so a increase of temperature encourages fluoride ion adsorption. As indicated in Table 4, ΔS° values for the adsorption process are positive. This observation suggests a high degree of disorderliness at the solid-solution interface during the adsorption of fluoride onto AVC. This may be due to the fact that the adsorbed water molecules, which

are displaced by the adsorbate species, gain more translational entropy than is lost by the adsorbate molecules, thus allowing the prevalence of randomness in the system¹⁷.

Kinetics of adsorption : The kinetics of fluoride removal has been carried out, using Natarajan and Khalaf model¹⁸, to understand the behavior of the adsorbent employed. The forward (k_1) and backward (k_2) rate constants were calculated as described in the literature¹⁹ and are furnished in Table 5 along with the rate constant for adsorption, k_{ad} . It is evident, from the results, that at lower fluoride concentrations and at higher temperatures, the forward rate constant is much higher than the backward rate constant suggesting that the rate of adsorption is clearly dominant.

Table 5. Rate constants for the adsorption of fluoride ($10^3 k_{\text{ad}}$, min^{-1}) and rate constants for the forward ($10^3 k_1$, min^{-1}) and reverse ($10^3 k_2$, min^{-1}) processes

[F ⁻] ₀	Temp. (°C)								
	k_{ad}			30		40		50	
	30°	40°	50°	k_1	k_2	k_1	k_2	k_1	k_2
2	7.14	7.97	8.29	3.91	3.23	4.61	3.36	5.09	3.20
4	5.92	6.15	8.13	2.89	3.03	3.38	2.77	4.95	3.18
6	4.58	5.71	8.02	2.09	2.49	3.06	2.65	4.72	3.30
8	2.95	4.21	7.37	1.22	1.73	1.89	2.32	4.21	3.16
10	1.03	2.42	6.29	0.42	0.61	1.05	1.37	3.12	3.17

The values of k_{ad} were found to decrease with increase in the initial concentration of fluoride from 2 to 10 mg L^{-1} . An examination of the effect of fluoride ion concentration on the k_{ad} helps to describe the mechanism of removal taking place. In cases of strict surface adsorption, a variation of rate should be proportional to the first power of concentration. However, when pore diffusion limits the adsorption process, the relationships between initial solute concentration and the rate of reaction will not be linear. Hence, it seems likely that pore diffusion limits the overall rate of fluoride adsorption²⁰. The possibility of intra-particle diffusion was tested by plotting the graph between amount of fluoride adsorbed and square root of time (Fig. 1). The initial curve portions, of these curves, are attributed to boundary layer diffusion effect and the final linear portions are due to intra-particle diffusion effect^{14,21}. In Fig. 3, the linear portions of the curves do not pass the origin. This indicates that the mechanism of removal of fluoride by AVC is complex and both the surface adsorption as well as intra-particle diffusion contributes to the rate-determining step^{14,18,21}.

Table 4. Equilibrium constants and thermodynamic parameters for the adsorption of fluoride onto AVC

[F ⁻] ₀	K_o			ΔG°			ΔH°	ΔS°
	30°	40°	50°	30°	40°	50°		
2	1.210	1.372	1.587	-0.48	-0.82	-1.24	10.7	36.9
4	0.951	1.217	1.554	0.13	-0.51	-1.18	19.4	63.6
6	0.840	1.154	1.429	0.44	-0.37	-0.96	21.1	68.3
8	0.704	0.818	1.332	0.88	0.52	-0.77	25.0	79.1
10	0.688	0.761	0.984	0.94	0.71	0.04	14.1	43.0

ΔG° , kJ mol^{-1} ; ΔH° , kJ mol^{-1} ; ΔS° , $\text{J K}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$.

Fig. 1. Intra-particle diffusion plot for the adsorption of fluoride onto AVC.

Effect of co-ions : The effect of added co-ions viz. Cl^- , NO_3^- , SO_4^{2-} and HCO_3^- on the percentage of adsorption is depicted in Fig. 2. The results indicate that the adsorption of fluoride is not adversely affected by the presence of other ions in solution thus making the adsorbent selective to fluoride. However, increase in concentration of bicarbonate ions drastically reduced the fluoride uptake. This may be due to the fact that there may be a competition between bicarbonate and fluoride ions for the active

Fig. 2. Effect of co-ions on the adsorption of fluoride onto AVC.

sites on the adsorbent and a similar observation was made, in the adsorption of fluoride, earlier^{13-15,18}.

XRD studies : Adsorption reaction may lead to changes in molecular and crystalline structure of the adsorbent and hence an understanding of the molecular and crystalline structures of the adsorbent and the resulting changes thereof would provide valuable information regarding adsorption reaction²². Hence, XRD patterns of the adsorbent before and after treatment with fluoride ions have been studied. It is evident from the XRD study that the crystal structure of the adsorbent showed no significant changes after the adsorption of fluoride ions. This suggests that the uptake of fluoride ions by the adsorbent is by physisorption^{14,22}.

Comparison with other adsorbents : Adsorption isotherms for fluoride in aqueous solution were compared for different adsorbents and the values of Langmuir parameters for the adsorption of fluoride in different adsorbents used in the literature with the adsorbent of the present study are summarized in Table 6. Although direct comparison of AVC with other adsorbents is difficult, owing to the different applied experimental conditions, it was found, in general, that the adsorption capacity of AVC for fluoride is comparable with that of other adsorbents and in fact greater than certain adsorbents reported earlier.

Test with field samples : The utility of the adsorbent has been tested by treating natural water samples collected from tube well water sources located at Myladumparai (sample 1) and Kadamalaikundu (sample 2) of Theni District, Tamil Nadu, S. India. Compositions (all in mg/L except pH) of the waters are, respectively, pH : 7.1, 7.4; total alkalinity : 500, 495; total hardness : 800, 500; total dissolved solids : 1960, 1950; NO_3^- : 15,

Table 6. Langmuir isotherm parameters for adsorption of fluoride from aqueous solution on different adsorbents

Adsorbent	Langmuir constants		Ref.
	Q_0 (mg/g)	b (L/mg)	
Activated alumina	2.41	0.31	25
Fluorspar	1.79	0.091	3
Activated quartz	1.16	0.086	3
Hydroxyapatite	4.54	2.44	3
Calcite	0.39	0.023	3
Quartz	0.19	0.12	3
Titanium rich bauxite	3.70	0.29	26
Plaster of Paris	0.366	0.830	15
AVC	0.389	0.171	Present work

28; Cl^- : 500, 550; F^- : 2.1, 1.6; SO_4^{2-} : 140, 150. The percentage removal of fluoride, at 30 °C, by the adsorbent from samples 1 and 2 were found to be 50 and 62 respectively which is in close agreement with the results mentioned above.

Conclusion : In batch adsorption studies, data show that AVC has considerable potential for the removal of fluoride ions from aqueous solutions. Wide range of pH and high temperature ranges were found as the optimum conditions for maximum fluoride adsorption by the adsorbent. The thermodynamics of the system pointed out the physisorption was spontaneous and endothermic.

Experimental

All the reagents used were of commercially available high purity AnalaR grade (SRL, India/sd-fine, India). The activated carbon was prepared by treating *Aloe vera* skin with concentrated sulphuric acid (1 : 1, w/v). The material was washed with distilled water to remove excess of acid and activated at 400 °C in a furnace. Grinding the material, followed by sieving gave the adsorbent. The methodology adopted for the characterization of the adsorbent and for batch sorption studies are the same as described earlier^{15,18}. The pH_{ZPC} was estimated as reported earlier²³ and the plot is shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. pH_{ZPC} curve.

The water quality parameters of the filed samples employed in the present study were estimated by conventional chemical and analytical methods²⁴.

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